

Socio - Economic Impacts of 2019 Flood Disaster in Upper Krishna Basin: Palus Taluka (Tal. Palus, Dist. Sangli, Maharashtra)

Mr. Maske Satish Ashok¹ and Mr. Kundle Sagar Ramrao²

¹ & ² Assistant Professor Dr. Patangrao Kadam Mahavidyalaya, Ramanandnagar (Burla)

Corresponding Author - Mr. Maske Satish Ashok

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.20293272

Abstract:

Floods, as natural disasters cause enormous economic and social losses to the Indian economy and cause immense suffering to the densely populated rural and urban populations living along the river banks of India. They are a major concern for most nations or states. Floods are always a major natural disaster that causes huge socio-economic losses. All the villages in the revenue Mandal of Palus Taluka in Sangli district are submerged during floods. These flood-affected villages in the Mandal division of Palus Taluka are located on both banks of the Krishna River and were heavily affected in the 2019 flood. The main objective of this research paper is to analyze the socio-economic impacts of the flood disaster that occurred in 2019.

Keywords: River Basin, Natural Hazards, Agriculture, Flood Disasters, Socio - Economic Impacts, Chemical Fertilizers.

Introduction:

Natural hazards, which damage national economies and create hardship for large segments of the population, are one of the greatest concerns for most nations. Human settlements frequently face natural disasters such as floods, earthquakes, cyclones, hurricanes, landslides, volcanic eruptions, which has a major impact on human life, destroys buildings and infrastructure and has economic and social consequences on communities (Randhir Singh Sangwan, 1999) The socio-economic environment is always affected by natural disasters and especially floods. India faces flood problems in some part of the country every year and about 12.5 percent of its geographical area is under flood water (Gautam, Alka, 2007). Maharashtra and especially Sangli district have been affected by floods in recent times (Patil, Sardar A. and Gatade, D. G., 2007). Low-lying villages and hamlets on the banks of the Krishna river in Sangli district have been

submerged during floods (Government of Maharashtra, 1972). There has been a huge increase in the number of floods in the low-lying villages on the banks of the Krishna River in Sangli district. Due to these floods, the agricultural areas along the banks go under water. This directly and indirectly affects many businesses. All this has an impact on the socio-economic condition of the area. If the flood situation continues in that region, unemployment and crime increase.

Study Area:

Palus Taluka is one of the most floods - prone Taluka of Sangli district. In Palus Taluka, a large number of flood problems arise on the banks of Krishna River. Palus Taluka is located at 17° 05' 00" N latitude 74° 28' 00" E longitude. This Taluka, located in the west of Sangli district, was established in the year 1999. The geographical location of Palus Taluka is in the

middle of Kadegaon and Khanapur Taluka in the north, Miraj Taluka in the south, Walwa Taluka in the west and Tasgaon in the east.

Objectives:

This research study has assessed the impact of the flood disaster in Sangli district, especially in Palus Taluka, in 2019. The main objective of this study is to analyze the socio-economic impact of the flood disaster that occurred in 2019. However, the specific objectives of this study are -

1. To assess the social impact of the floods that occurred in the study area during 2019.
2. To study the impact of flood disasters on agriculture, transport facilities, shops and agricultural workers.

Research Methodology:

This research paper is based on primary as well as secondary data. However, primary data is the main source to fulfill the objectives of the study. Therefore, correlative data has been collected by conducting in-depth field work during the post - flood period. Stratified sampling method has been used to select households to

collect data related to the impact of the 2019 flood disaster. A schedule has been used for this purpose. During the field inspection, observation method as well as informal personal interaction with some individuals has been used to verify the data provided by other individuals. Google Earth satellite imagery has been used to understand the topography, for data collection and data analysis. Other relevant secondary data has been collected through SOI topographic maps, books, journals, newspapers and several websites etc. which are specified under the heading of references.

After collecting primary and secondary data, it has been processed. The processed data has been tabulated and presented in the form of charts and figures.

Consequences of Flood Disaster:

Flood is the most common environmental hazard; due to the wide geographical distribution of river valleys and coastal areas and the attraction of human settlements to these areas (Kevalramani, Geeta, 2006). Floods have occurred in some parts of the country and hence flood is the oldest phenomenon in India (Singh, Mahendra, 2008). Floods are common in the Krishna River delta. However, this was not a common occurrence in the upper Krishna valley, especially in Sangli district. But in recent times, due to the increase in the height of dams in Karnataka, the water level of the Krishna River increases rapidly during the monsoon season and its result is a huge problem like floods. Recently, especially in 2019, the flood in the Krishna River valley in Palus Taluka of Sangli district of Maharashtra was unexpected and long-lasting for the first time in history.

A devastating flood situation occurred in Sangli district between 27 July and 13 August 2019. All the villages on the banks of the Krishna River in Palus Taluka were the most affected by the flood. Mandal-wise, the villages in Bhilwadi

revenue Mandal were the most affected by the flood. Then, Ankalkhop, Kundal and the least affected villages in Palus revenue division were the most affected.

The Krishna River crossed the danger level in Palus Taluka of Sangli district during the severe floods in August 2019. The flood waters of August 2019 broke all previous records, the highest flood level recorded in the flood-affected village of Palus Taluka. M. S. L. was 556.9 meters. The flood warning level is 40 feet and the flood danger level is 45 feet.

1. Impact of floods on Agriculture:

The floods in Palus Taluka in 2019 destroyed crops and agricultural land in a total area of 29700 hectares in four revenue divisions. Sugarcane is the major cash crop in Palus taluka. The 2019 floods affected 29.38% of the total area under sugarcane. The 2019 floods were the main cause of economic loss in Palus Taluka.

In Palus Taluka, crops like sugarcane, groundnut, soybean, rice, vegetables, banana plantations etc. were damaged to a large extent. After sugarcane, groundnut was the crop most affected by the flood disaster. It was 5.19% of the total area. The 2019 flood waters had affected 2.46% of the soybean area, while 3.11% of the area was affected by the rice crop. Along with these crops, 2.87% of the area of other crops was affected. The various crops damaged are shown in the table.

According to the revenue department of Palus Taluka, the agricultural area in Bhilwadi Mandal was the most affected. This was followed by the agricultural areas in Ankalkhop and Kundal revenue Mandals. The agricultural area in Palus revenue Mandal was the least affected.

Table 1.1 Impacts of Flood on crops in Palus Taluka Percentage (%)

Crops	Sugarcane	Groundnut	Rice	Soyabean	Other Crops
(%)	29.38	5.13	3.11	2.46	2.87

2. Impact on Livestock:

There was no direct damage to livestock in the Krishna River Valley of Palus Taluka. However, indirect flood conditions caused a shortage of fodder and this affected milk production. Due to the flood conditions, the transport system was disrupted, so the available milk did not find a market, which also resulted in financial losses to the farmers.

3. Impact of floods on Homes:

The devastating floods in Palus Taluka in 2019 affected 17607 families in four revenue mandals of Bhilwadi, Kundal, Palus and Ankalkhop. Out of the total affected families, 70% of the families were completely affected by the floods. Entire families in the villages of Dahyari, Burli, Amnapur, Santgaon, Suryagaon, Bramhanal, Khatav, Ankalkhop, Bhilwadi, Anugadewadi, Chopdewadi, Sukhwadi, Burungwadi in Palus Taluka were affected.

Clothes, utensils, food grains, TVs and other valuables in the village, which was completely affected by the flood, were completely damaged. The houses in the village, which was completely affected by the flood, were submerged in water, causing cracks in the houses. The roofs were cracked and the walls of some houses had completely collapsed.

According to the revenue department of Palus Taluka, the maximum number of houses in Bhilwadi mandal was affected. After that, the agricultural areas in Ankalkhop and Kundal revenue mandals were affected. While the houses in Palus revenue Mandal were affected the least.

Table 1.2 Impacts of Flood on Homes in Palus Taluka

Sr. No	Mandal Name	Number of House Affected
1	Kundal	3274
2	Palus	2470
3	Ankalkhop	3784
4	Bhilwadi	8079

4. Impact on Shops and other Economic Activities:

The flood disaster caused a loss of Rs 500 crore in Sangli district. The floods that occurred between July 27 and August 13 had an economic impact on shops in villages across four revenue boards. Due to this devastating flood, shops in villages across four revenue boards were submerged, causing losses worth crores of rupees to shopkeepers. Every village had shops selling chemical fertilizers for agriculture. About thousands of tons of damage were caused in the 2019 floods.

Also, cattle rearing are a sideline activity on the banks of the Krishna River in Palus Taluka and milk production is also done from there. Due to this flood, the transportation system collapsed for more than ten to fifteen days. Due to this, the financial support from milk production was lost to a great extent.

According to the revenue department in Palus Taluka, the highest financial loss was suffered in Bhilwadi mandal. It was followed by Ankalkhop and Kundal revenue mandals. The lowest financial loss was suffered in Palus revenue Mandal.

5. Impact of floods on health:

The floods that occurred in August 2019 had an adverse impact on human health along the Krishna River in Palus Taluka. The devastating floods that occurred in 2019 killed 17 people in Brahmanal village. However, 26 people were

seriously injured after being swept away by the floodwaters.

After the 2019 floods receded, many epidemics had struck the villages along the Krishna River, with dengue, diarrhea, vomiting, fever, etc., increasing.

The Palus administration had taken precautionary measures at the right time and hence there were no adverse effects on human health. According to the revenue department of Palus Taluka, the highest number of epidemics had spread in Bhilwadi mandal. Following that, epidemics had spread in Ankalkhop and Kundal revenue mandals. While the lowest number of epidemics had spread in Palus revenue Mandal.

6. Impact on Basic Amenities:

In the study area, basic amenities and human needs like food, clothing, shelter, health, education, transportation and water were affected in the villages of four revenue divisions in 2019. Due to the unexpected flood water and the nature of the flood, the food stored in four revenue divisions in Palus Taluka was completely destroyed. The problem of scarcity of drinking water due to the flood is also at the forefront. In the study area, the drinking water facilities of 25 villages had collapsed due to flood water. This led to many water-borne diseases during the flood disaster and after the flood receded. At the same time, the people of the flood-affected villages had to face many problems due to the disruption of the transport system.

7. Positive Impacts:

The devastating floods of 2019 have had some positive impacts along with the devastating impacts. Based on the field work conducted by the researchers along the Krishna River in Palus Taluka after the flood receded and the feedback from the farmers, there are some beneficial impacts. The major positive impacts observed in the study area are as follows.

1. The flood has increased the groundwater level in the agricultural land in Palus Taluka.
2. The accumulation of sediment on the land that became saline due to the flood of 2019 has helped improve the soil quality on the banks of the Krishna.
3. The flood of 2019 has caused the accumulation of about four to eight centimeters of fertile sediment in the area along the banks of the Krishna River. Due to the accumulation of sediment, fertile land was created for agriculture. After that, good crop production was obtained from that farm.

Conclusion:

Floods occurring along the river banks are one of the natural disasters that affect the socio-economic condition of the community in the flood-affected areas. The floods in the upper Krishna valley in 2019 were one of the worst floods in the history of the river valley. The floods in 2019 had a devastating impact on the socio-economic condition of the villages in four revenue mandals of Palus Taluka.

In 2019, 30,500 farmers were directly affected by the floods. They lost crops worth Rs 50 to 100 crore. Similarly, houses, food grains, farm implements and other valuable assets were damaged to the tune of Rs 50 crore. The floods had a major impact on transport facilities, grocery stores and chemical fertilizer shops, milk production, village infrastructure, village livestock, houses, temples, schools. Electricity wires and poles, etc. During the flood, many health problems were also found in Palus Taluka, revenue division wise.

Also, in Palus Taluka, due to the rapid flow of water along the revenue Mandal-wise slope, a large amount of soil erosion of the upper layer of agricultural land occurred, which

subsequently reduced the productivity of the land. Along with the adverse socio-economic impacts, positive impacts have also been observed in the study area. These are increase in groundwater level, increase in soil fertility, and reduction in the problem of salinization.

References:

1. **Gautam, Alka (2007):** Environmental Geography, Sharda Pustak Bhawan, Allahabad, p. 205.
2. Government of Maharashtra (1972): Gazetteer of Sangli District.
3. <http://www.maharashtraonline/asp/url/Sangli/himl/>
4. **Kewalramani, Gita (2006):** Geomorphic Effectiveness of High Magnitude Floods in the Tapi River: Evaluation based on hydrographs and streams power graphs, Transactions, Institute of Indian Geographers, Vol. No. 1 PP 24-39.
5. **Patil Sardar A & Patil Shilpa S (2011)** Socio-Economic Impacts Of Flood Disaster In Upper Krishna Basin: A Case Study of Village Pundi (Tal. Palus, Dist. Sangli, Maharashtra)' Vol. No. 1 PP 19-26
6. **Patil, Sardar A. and Gatade D. G. (2007):** "A Geographical Perspective of Flood Affected Villages: A Case Study of Haripur (Sangli District)", The Goa Geographer, Vol. IV, pp-89-93.
7. Randhir Singh Sangwan (1999): Flood situation at Rohatak. Transactions Institute of Indian Geographers, Vol. 21, No. 2, p. 65.
8. **Singh, Mahendra (2008):** Natural Calamities in India, Satyam Publishing House, New Delhi, P. 188.
9. **Basu Swapna and Santra, S. (1988):** Flood problems of Howarah District, Geographical Review of India, Vol. 50, No. 4, pp. 69-74.

10. **Bose, B.C. (2007):** Global Disasters Vulnerability and Precautionary Principle, Rajat Publications, New Delhi, p.1.
11. **Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2005).** Leptospirosis. Technical information. Available from: http://www.cdc.gov/ncidod/dbmd/diseaseinfo/leptospirosis_t.htm. [Cited on 2006 Jul 30].
12. Centre for Science and Environment “State of India’s Environment: A Citizens’ Report 3 on Floods, Floodplains and Environmental Myths” New Delhi, 1991.
13. Choen Kim and Kwang-Hoon Chi: Flood Damage Mapping in North Korea Using Multi-Sensor Data, <http://www.gisdevelopment.net/aars/acrs/1998/ts3/ts3001a.asp>
14. **Critchfield, H.J.(1987):** General Climatology, 4th Edition, Prentice - Hall Inc. Englewood Cliffs, N.J., U.S.A. P.258.
15. **Dinand Alkema (2004):** Remote Sensing and GIS Application in Flood Forecasting. <http://www.itc.nl/>
16. Dinand Alkema and Muhammad Zulkarnain Abd Rahman: Digital Surface Model (DSM) Construction and Flood Hazard Simulation for Development Plans in Naga City, Philippines, http://www.gisdevelopment.net/application/natural_hazards/floods/mm037_1.htm